

1 **Xist controls GLI3 activation.**

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6 Oncogenes and homeobox transcription factors signal amongst each other and in response to one
7 another during transformation and repair of the DNA in following damage of the DNA. We identified a
8 homeobox transcription factor cascade that is required for transformation in human cells including PAX8
9 and HoxC/D family members. Homeobox factors that control transformation in humans likely reside in
10 hierarchically-defined positions. Evidence has suggested GLI factor expression occurs early in the
11 induction of malignancy during transformation. We describe transcriptional control of the GLI family
12 homeobox factor *GLI3* by Xist. The data support Xist regulation of homeobox factors as a general
13 biological property of the Xist non-coding RNA that served as a paradigm for regulation of embryonic
14 development and the cancer life cycle program by Xist. Xist controls fate choice through homeobox factor
15 regulation; this homeotic factor induction by the non-coding RNA during developmental transitions appears
16 to occur early, or more proximal to nuclear events that precede malignant transformation. Together we
17 describe hierarchically-informed Xist homeobox regulation of transformation.
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